

Library Reprographic Policy, E-library policy and Service Delivery in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationships among library reprographic policy, e-library policy, and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Two research questions guided this study, and hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level. The study employed a correlational research design. The population consisted of 115 professional librarians from eight federal universities in South-South Nigeria, namely: University of Benin (UNIBEN), University of Calabar, University of Port Harcourt, University of Uyo, Federal University of Technology, Ikot-Abasi, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, Nigerian Maritime University, Okerenkoko, Delta State, and Federal University, Otuoke. Since the population was small, a census approach was adopted, with the entire population as the sample. A structured questionnaire with a 4-point Likert scale was used to collect data. Face and content validation of the instrument were adopted. A trial testing technique ensured the instrument's reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha yielding a coefficient of 0.8. Data analysis utilised Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) via the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The results revealed a significant relationship between library reprographic policy, e-library policy, and service delivery. Based on these findings, the following recommendation is made: Library management should place greater emphasis on ensuring adherence to copyright law within the library. Also, library management should seek government support to employ professional ICT librarians to manage their E-library.

Keywords: Library, Reprographic Policy, E-library Policy, Service Delivery

Introduction

A library consists of books and other materials organised for use. This study examines how library reprographic policies, e-library policies, and service delivery relate to each other. According to Anyira (2021), a "policy" is a set of specific actions or rules officially adopted by a group, organisation, or government. Without a policy, an organisation is like a vehicle without direction. Further, Anyira (2021) explains that library policies include collection development, circulation/lending, cataloguing, reference, serials/periodicals, document reproduction/reprographic, and e-library policies. Each section within a library operates under its own guiding policy. Reprographic policy specifically governs the duplication of published images or texts. Reprography, a form of reproduction, involves copying published materials through mechanical or electronic means. According to the Artists Rights Society (2024), the term

reprography combines "reproduce" and "photography." It produces a copy of a graphic image or text via methods such as printing, photocopying, scanning, digitising, electronic transmission like faxing, or electronic storage in databases.

In reprographic policy, all requests to reproduce copyrighted material must include information identifying the source, such as the author/creator, publisher, date of publication, title of the book for a book chapter, and URL for web-based material. The policy regarding photocopying states that no more than 20 pages should be copied from the original. There is poor adherence to the reprographic policy in some institutions, as some personnel handling this section are not professional librarians. This impacts the effective implementation of reproduction and reprographic policies.

Ubogu (2013) stated that the E-library policy is the set of conditions, rules, terms, and regulations governing every aspect of the Digital Library service. These include acceptable user behaviour, digital rights management, privacy and confidentiality, user charges, and collection formation. A digital library, also known as an e-library, is a collection of documents in an organised digital form, available on the internet or on disks. The purpose of an e-library is to store, access, and manage magazine articles, books, audio files, images, and video files. Online e-resources include: E-journals (full text & bibliographic), E-books, online databases, and websites. E-library services save users' time locating information and help them access current information resources on the internet. Poor implementation of the E-library policy affects the service delivery of the library. The e-library needs to have a 24/7 uninterrupted power supply and internet service to meet users' needs. Some university managements that are not library-friendly pay little attention to funding the library, which leads to poor implementation of E-library policies and affects the section's service delivery.

Service delivery is the act of providing a service to clients or customers. Service delivery involves effectively discharging duties to meet the client's information needs. Uganneya (2011) opines that library service delivery is a set of mechanisms whose interactions determine the effectiveness of library and information services.

This research focuses exclusively on federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Federal universities are tertiary education institutions managed and operated by the Federal Government of Nigeria. In most federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria, service delivery is hampered by poor management of reprographic policies, resulting from a lack of attention, poor adherence to reprographic guidelines, and inadequate implementation of e-library policies. This is mainly due to the indifferent attitude of librarians and inexperienced staff lacking library and information science qualifications. This study aims to enhance library service delivery in federal universities within South-South Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Effective library reprographic and e-library policies are essential for guiding academic library services toward meeting their objectives. Proper implementation of these policies is crucial for delivering quality services. Based on personal observations and interactions with librarians, several challenges impede service delivery in Nigerian university libraries, such as poor management of reprographic policies and inadequate enforcement of e-library policies. These issues primarily affect federal universities in South-South Nigeria. Even though policies exist across various university library departments, their failure to be implemented continues to cause problems. This study explores the connection between reprographic policies, e-library policies, and service delivery in these federal universities.

Objectives of the study

The main aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between the library reprographic policy, e-library policy, and service delivery in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Identify the relationship between the library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.
2. Establish the relationship between the E-Library policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 significance level.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the E-Library policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Library information policy:

Case (2010) defines library and information policy as the laws, regulations, and practices that facilitate the creation and sharing of information within society. These policies support the development and dissemination of information to enable effective delivery of library services. Library policies are those laws that govern all library activities. Obi and Mmejim (2019) noted a significant gap between the development of information policies and their implementation. To bridge this widening gap, they suggest that the development of such policies should focus on the information needs of citizens and the knowledge custodians, who are the key stakeholders.

Reprography policy:

According to the University of Nottingham (2022), reprographic policy defines the rules for copying, including what can be copied, how much, the methods used, and the intended purposes. It governs the duplication of published images or texts, supporting the copying of essential library materials to ensure effective service delivery. Reproduction is a key activity within libraries. The policy's scope covers general regulations, copyright laws, photocopying, photography, microform printouts, image prints, film, sound recordings, and the acknowledgement and referencing of sources in publications.

Reprographic involves making additional copies from the original or an existing copy, and there are policies guiding its activities. To ensure that reprographic services are not abused, effective adherence to these policies becomes essential. In line with this, according to Borough of Manhattan Community College (2023), Reprographic aims to ensure that copying complies with copyright law. To achieve this, the rule states that: All requests for reproduction of copyrighted material must include information identifying the source of the material (e.g., author/creator, publisher, date of publication, title of the book if the document is a book chapter, URL for web-based material).

All requests for copies will be reviewed by the reprographics department to ensure copyright compliance and fair use when appropriate. Faculty and staff submitting materials with questions about copyright compliance may be asked to provide additional information. In some cases, reprographic may decline to make copies if it is likely to violate copyright laws, such as copying an entire book or play. Reprographic

can copy materials that are in the public domain, for which the requester holds the copyright, or for which permission has been received from the author or creator. It can also copy material with Creative Commons or other open licenses, where copying falls under the fair use provision of copyright law.

According to Oregon State University (2023), Title 17, section 108 of the U.S. Code allows libraries and archives to use copyrighted materials under specific conditions without needing permission from the copyright owner. Oregon State University clarified that this section permits libraries and archives to: make a single copy of an item for interlibrary loan; create up to three copies of a damaged, lost, or stolen work for replacement when a fair-priced copy isn't available; produce up to three copies of unpublished works for preservation, with digital copies not circulating outside the library; reproduce, distribute, display, or perform works in their last 20 years of copyright for preservation, research, or scholarship if they are unavailable at a fair price or are under commercial exploitation; and make one copy of an entire work upon request if the work isn't available at a fair price. Reprographic services support university libraries in resource sharing.

Sambo, Aghojare, and Ahutu (2016) stated that the primary aim of reprographic units in theological institutions' libraries is to reduce the cost of printing, photocopying, and other related services provided to library users compared with other reprographic business centres both within and outside the academic institution. Other aims of reprographic services include the dissemination of information on a large scale among libraries and between libraries and their patrons, the reproduction of documents, and the prevention of the mutilation of library resources by users.

A reprographic policy is essential in libraries to manage reproduction activities effectively. Udochukwu (2019) states that reprography plays various roles in libraries, such as spreading information widely among libraries and with users, copying and preserving records, ensuring security, storing documents, and protecting information. Because these roles require proper guidance, it is vital for all academic libraries to have a reprographic policy. This policy helps coordinate reprographic activities, meet users' information needs, and improve service delivery.

Challenges to the effective implementation of reprographic policy in university libraries include librarians' need for adequate knowledge of the policy. This knowledge should encompass copyright laws governing copying and photocopying of materials in the public domain. Often, these laws are not followed, which hampers the effective implementation of the reprographic policy.

Igbege (2009) observed that some problems associated with reprographic policy include "lack of spare parts and funding." Funding plays a very important role in the implementation of reprographic policy; when a library is underfunded, every activity, including policy implementation, will be at a standstill, which can pose a serious issue, as the library needs money to run efficiently and effectively. The funding problem becomes more acute now that library operations are expensive to run, including staff welfare and training. With dwindling allocations to the library, management finds it difficult to maintain staff training, promotions, and salary increases, which, in turn, demoralises staff, leads to a poor attitude towards work, and affects the effective implementation of reprographic policy.

Similarly, Udochukwu (2019) states that funding is a major constraint on reprographic activities in Nigeria. Beyond the costs of acquiring reprographic equipment, funds are also necessary to motivate workers to follow the policies while providing services. Reprographic policy requires both human and material resources to operate effectively. Factors that may hinder the successful implementation of this policy include unskilled staff and inconsistent power supply. Regular training will equip librarians with current knowledge of reprographic policies and guide their proper implementation.

Strategies for addressing the challenges of reprographic policy. Udochukwu (2019) recommended strategies to address reprographic challenges, including effective and efficient library management, adequate library funding, and staff training and retraining through seminars, workshops, and conferences. The government should also establish policies on reprographic services, and maintenance of facilities should be carried out by reprographic operators through regular servicing. If these strategies are implemented, it will lead to the effective execution of reprographic policy.

Akalumhe et al. (2019) concluded that copyright law provides protection to creators and producers of information resources. It also balances the promotion of users' interests with the rights of creators. It is unfortunate that, despite the strict criminal provisions and penalties in our legal system, illegal photocopying of library books still persists. Furthermore, it is important to note that photocopying information resources in libraries could harm authors and publishers. Likewise, it has been observed that copyright law in Nigeria is often treated with levity within libraries. Clifford and Oghenenyehovwome (2014) found that copyright law violations could be reduced through effective policies from the Nigeria Copyright Commission.

Akalumhe, et al. maintain that: Librarians are expected to educate their users, especially on copyright law, to ensure that authors can enjoy the fruits of their labour. Regular workshops, seminars, and conferences should be organised at higher institutions to further inform staff and students about the importance and benefits of copyright for owners and the government. Copyright commission inspectors, police, and other security agents should intensify their efforts in regularly arresting and prosecuting copyright offenders. This would significantly reduce the illegal and covert activities of violators of copyright laws. University libraries should ensure that copyright warnings are clearly displayed at strategic locations within the library. Additionally, libraries should develop policies on handling copyrighted materials, particularly concerning photocopying.

Effective implementation of a reprographic policy in a university library will enhance the availability, accessibility, and effective use of reprographic resources and improve library service delivery.

E-library Policy

The e-library policy, also known as digital or virtual library policy, outlines the rules, conditions, terms, and regulations that govern all aspects of digital library services. This includes acceptable user behavior, digital rights management, privacy and confidentiality, user charges, and collection development. Hanna (2022) describes a digital library as a collection of digital objects—such as books, magazines, audio recordings, videos, and other documents—that are accessible electronically. The activities within digital libraries are guided by this policy. Several reasons drive the development of digital libraries, including the information explosion, limited library budgets, space constraints, high demand for information, and advancements in technology. Just as there are strong reasons to establish digital libraries, it is equally important to have a comprehensive policy to oversee their operations. Regarding copyright and content digitization, Oregon State University (2023) notes that materials in the public domain can be digitized without permission or restrictions. Additionally, libraries may digitize parts of their collections for specific purposes under fair use provisions.

Digital Library Rules and Regulations according to Aabasaheb and Kamalabai Sardeshpande Central Library (2023) include: College identification (I.D.) is compulsory to access the digital/e-library; the Digital Library is to be used solely for academic and research purposes; login identifications (I.D.'s) and passwords for various e-resources or online resources will be communicated to students and faculty members periodically. Access to these resources will be internet protocol (I.P.) based and cannot be

accessed beyond the boundaries of the college campus. Members must not share their net access I.D. and password with other students. Changing the settings and display of the computers kept in the digital library is not permitted. Users should handle computers, hardware, software, and accessories carefully. Online chatting in the digital library is not allowed. Browsing dating and social networking sites is strictly prohibited; strict disciplinary action will be taken against those who violate this rule. Playing games on computers is strictly prohibited throughout the entire library premises. Members are not allowed to carry eatables and drinks anywhere within the library premises. Members must take care of their pen drives, CD/DVD ROMs, cell phones, wallets, etc.

According to the Government of the Punjab (2023), the E-Library Rules & Regulations include specific guidelines: visitors are responsible for their personal belongings, such as handbags and briefcases, which should be left outside the library entrance; the library is not liable for any loss or damage. Do not write, underline, or mark any books, as mutilating library materials can result in hefty fines and disciplinary actions. After reading, kindly leave books on the table or the book trolley—do not reshelve them. Maintain complete silence, except for brief, quiet conversations with the staff. Mobile phones should be turned off or kept silent within the library. Eating and drinking are not allowed, except for drinking water. Smoking, including electronic cigarettes, and the use of alcohol or drugs are strictly forbidden inside the library.

Others include: Short pants and other inappropriate dresses are strictly not allowed in the library. Do not alter the configuration of computers or other equipment. Senior citizens and individuals with special needs should be given priority. Permission is required to use the auditorium and discussion rooms. Do not relocate furniture, fixtures, computer hardware, or other library items. Access to administrative offices, stores, security devices, electric panels, and other restricted areas is prohibited for library users. Antisocial, harassing, or threatening behavior is not tolerated. Offenders will be asked to leave, and repeat offenders will face indefinite bans. The use of obscene or abusive language or gestures is strictly discouraged. Carrying weapons such as knives or guns on library premises is strictly prohibited. Some items in the library cannot be copied due to copyright laws, poor condition, or donor restrictions.

Radboud University (2023) specifies the terms and conditions for digital library users: Users must adhere to the proper use of digital resources—such as data files, software, and media—limited to academic research, education, and study purposes. Commercial use is strictly forbidden, and resources cannot be used on behalf of organizations or companies outside the university. All use is governed by standard copyright laws. Printing and downloading individual journal articles or book chapters is allowed only for personal use. Systematic downloading, distribution, printing, or storing large portions of licensed materials is prohibited. Additionally, publishing licensed content online or through electronic networks is not permitted.

Challenges facing e-library policy: As Ibanga (2022) highlights, issues in Nigerian e-libraries include the high cost of establishment, which is significant even for physical libraries. Governments, NGOs, private, and public enterprises are expected to fund these initiatives. Also, setting up cybercafés or business centers for library services is costly. Additionally, challenges in classifying and cataloging published works persist. While digital libraries are designed to facilitate classification and cataloging per international standards, many institutions struggle to encourage researchers and lecturers to publish their work according to these standards.

According to Ibanga, other issues include: Dependency on Technology - There is an over-reliance on technology to run computers or make the e-Library effective. Technologies are frequently upgraded with new software or applications, requiring adjustments or updates. The e-Library faces challenges in functioning properly without internet access and reliable electronic devices. Most Nigerian libraries lack

e-Libraries because access to information technology is limited. Training and Skills - Operating an e-Library demands substantial skills and training from users. Users must be able to access relevant materials and resources to gain knowledge and information. Training users on how to use the e-Library helps develop skills that can lead to employment. However, many Nigerian libraries lack staff with the necessary skills to operate an e-Library.

Copyright Issues: The digital or electronic library does not oversee piracy of intellectual property or the duplication of someone else's research, journals, or articles, which users might carry out. Researchers, academics, or lecturers may copy online works of others. Privacy Issues: The digital or electronic library does not guarantee the protection of published materials such as online journals, articles, books, and resource materials because it is easily accessible, allowing contents to be scanned or printed from a computer. Authors struggle to keep their works private online since the e-library makes all available content accessible to everyone. Power Supply Generation: Digital or electronic libraries rely heavily on a consistent power supply to operate. Nigeria struggles with inadequate power generation services.

Akpan and Eni (2019) highlighted challenges in implementing virtual library projects, including misconceptions about what constitutes a virtual library, lack of basic information infrastructure, poor policy execution, and a shortage of web technologies skilled digital and systems librarians. Effective policy success depends on all parts of the system functioning properly.

Baro et al. (2013) found that librarians attending the workshop gained skills in database searching, using various search engines, social media, relevant websites, and library planning. They expressed the view that such workshops should be held at least twice annually to enhance librarians' skills in Nigeria. Consequently, the workshop is essential for librarians to develop the competencies required for effective service delivery aligned with e-library policies.

Service delivery

Indeed, (2023) considers service delivery as a business framework that provides services from a provider to a client. It involves ongoing interactions between both parties throughout the duration of the service and the purchase. Service delivery is a process that demands strong management skills, proper planning, and thorough preparation. It encompasses many tasks and activities. The level of service delivery in an organization depends on the quality of the service provided. Focusing more on the delivery process allows for higher quality services to customers (Russell, 2021). The National Institute of Open Schooling (2023) stated that Ranganathan viewed the library as a trinity consisting of: Readers, Books, and Staff. In this model, books serve as knowledge containers, readers are the knowledge seekers, and staff are the facilitators or providers of library services to users. A library exists whenever and wherever these three elements—readers, books, and staff—are purposefully interacting. These components are interdependent and complement each other; effective service delivery requires their cooperation to achieve a common goal.

Effective service delivery relies on qualities such as empathy, problem-solving, active listening, and attentiveness. Library service providers should possess these qualities to perform their duties effectively. Obi (2016) explained that users' services encompass all services provided directly to library users, including lending materials, orientation, assistance, issuing guides, photocopying, opening the library, providing seating, and registration. All these services aim to meet users' needs.

According to the Republic of Uganda Ministry of Local Government (2013), international principles guiding effective service delivery include: Availability - a service should be accessible at the time and level required by the user; Dependability - a service should be delivered reliably and on schedule; Usability

- a service should be presented in formats suitable for the user so they can fully understand it; Usefulness - a service should be designed to meet user needs appropriately; Credibility - a service should be designed so that users can confidently and conveniently use it to solve their problems or needs; Authenticity - a service should be delivered in a manner that warrants acceptance by stakeholders in relevant decision-making contexts; Responsiveness and flexibility - a service should directly address the changing needs of users; Sustainability - a service should be affordable and maintainable over time; Expandability - a service should be adaptable to various approaches.

Russell (2021) stated that one of the main challenges of service delivery is time management. You have limited time and must work on different projects simultaneously. Therefore, it is difficult to manage your time according to your needs. Service delivery also requires collaborating with others to provide better services to clients. Hence, managing others' work is one of the biggest challenges associated with service delivery. Additionally, poor coordination between departments results in subpar service delivery within an organisation. This makes it one of the major hurdles faced by those involved in service delivery.

Adindu (2021) study found a significant relationship between Internet service delivery and user satisfaction at Federal University Libraries in South-South Nigeria, with users expressing satisfaction with the Internet services. The researcher emphasised that more effort and funding should be put in by the parent institutions of these academic libraries to maintain or improve current Internet services, as this meets user demands. Additionally, academic libraries should regularly train staff on the best practices for assisting patrons with Internet facilities. Providing reliable Internet services also requires a comprehensive e-library policy to ensure sustainable and effective operations.

Review of Empirical Studies

Reprographic policy: Clifford and Oghenenyerhovwome (2014) conducted a study on copyright law violations through photocopying at Delta State University, Abraka. The research focused on copyright infringement through photocopying in tertiary institutions, using a descriptive survey method. The population included 3,849 students at Delta State University, Abraka, with a sample size of 77. Data was collected using questionnaires, and simple percentages were used for analysis.

The findings revealed that effective policies from the Nigerian Copyright Commission could reduce violations of copyright law. The studies also showed that textbooks are the most frequently abused materials through photocopying, and penalties for copyright infringement are outlined in the Nigerian constitution. The study recommended that libraries develop better methods to enforce copyright law in tertiary institutions, and that the Nigeria Copyright Commission should actively address the issue and protect authors.

The above study is similar to the present one as both examine information policy within the realm of reprographic policy. Both utilised questionnaires as the data collection tool. However, the reviewed study employed a descriptive research design, whereas the current study used a correlational design. The reviewed study was conducted at Delta State University in Delta State, involving a total population of 3,849 students and a sample size of 77. In contrast, the current study was conducted across seven federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria, with a population of 115 professional librarians.

Akalumhe et al. (2019) conducted a study on photocopying and copyright violations in academic libraries, focusing on the Fatiu Ademola Akesode Library in Lagos. The objective was to assess the extent of photocopying and copyright law violations in Nigeria. The research employed a descriptive survey method. The population included all students at Lagos State University, with a sample of 1,300

respondents randomly selected from a total of 35,000 full-time students. Data was collected using a questionnaire. The analysis involved frequency tables and simple percentages.

The study reveals that most respondents are aware of Nigeria's copyright law, but still mainly rely on photocopying copyrighted materials for their studies. They agree that there are mild sanctions for copyright violations. Therefore, the study recommends that the Nigerian Copyright Commission strengthen its efforts to ensure that libraries at tertiary institutions in Nigeria penalise any copyright violations by photocopiers.

The above study closely relates to the current one because both focus on library information policies, specifically on library reprographic policy. Both studies use a structured questionnaire as their data collection tool. However, the reviewed study employed a descriptive research design, whereas the current study used a correlational design. The reviewed study was conducted at a Lagos library in Southwestern Nigeria, involving students from Lagos State University, which has a population of 35,000, with a sample size of 1,300. In contrast, the current study was conducted in libraries across seven federal universities in South-South Nigeria, with a population of 115 professional librarians, all of whom were included.

E-library policy: Okogwu and Ekere (2018) conducted a study on collection development policies for electronic resources in University Libraries across Southeast Nigeria. The research focused on the various policies that guide the development of electronic resource collections. A descriptive survey method was employed. The population consisted of 86 librarians involved in collection development, serials, and digital libraries within Southeast universities, and all 86 were included as the sample. Data was gathered through questionnaires and interviews. The analysis involved simple descriptive statistics, including percentages and mean scores.

The findings revealed that the university libraries studied adopted traditional policies. The study recommended that libraries formulate and develop a policy for the collection development of electronic resources; efforts should be made to establish a written policy for the collection development of electronic resources, which would serve as a guide and reference point to ensure continuity among librarians involved in e-resources collection development.

The above study is similar to the present study because both focus on library information policies, specifically e-library policies. Both studies use a constructed questionnaire as an instrument for data collection. However, the reviewed study employed a descriptive research design, while the current study employed a correlational research design. The reviewed study was carried out in university libraries in Southeast Nigeria, with a total population of 86 librarians, using all 86 as the sample size, while the current study was conducted in seven federal university libraries in South-South Nigeria, with a population of 115 professional librarians, and all 115 were used for the study.

Adindu (2021) carried out a study on Internet Services Delivery and Users' Satisfaction in Federal University Libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The study examined Internet service delivery guidelines and users' satisfaction. The study adopted a correlational research design. Data for the study were obtained through a questionnaire. With a population of 17,600 and a sample size of 1,760, means, frequency counts, and the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient were used for data analysis.

The study found a significant relationship between Internet service delivery and user satisfaction in Federal University libraries in South-South Nigeria, with users expressing satisfaction with the Internet services. Based on these results, it is recommended that the parent institutions allocate more effort and funds to maintaining or improving the current Internet services in their libraries, as this aligns with user preferences. The above study is similar to the present one because both focus on library information policies related to e-library services guidelines. The reviewed study used a correlational research design with a structured

questionnaire, as does the current study. It was conducted in university libraries in South-South Nigeria, and the present study was also carried out in university libraries in South-South Nigeria. However, the reviewed study involved a population of 17,600 library users with a sample size of 1,760, whereas the current study's population comprises 115 professional librarians, using the entire group of 115 for the study.

Methodology

The study employed a correlational research design. The population included 115 professional librarians from eight federal universities in South-South Nigeria: University of Benin (UNIBEN), University of Calabar, University of Port Harcourt, University of Uyo, Federal University of Technology, Ikot-Abasi, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, Nigerian Maritime University Okerenkoko, Delta State, and Federal University, Otuoke. The entire population of 115 librarians was sampled, using a census sampling method as recommended by Vedantu (2023), which states that census sampling is appropriate for small populations and yields more accurate results. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire utilizing Likert 4-point scales. The data were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlations (PPMC) to address the research questions and test hypotheses, which were evaluated at a 0.05 level of significance. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to ensure the accuracy of the analysis. The research findings are presented in the table below, with corresponding explanations.

Research Question One:

What is the relationship between the library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria?

Hypothesis One: There is no significant link between the library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 2: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between the library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Correlations				
S/N	Items		Library reprographic policy	Service Delivery
1	Library reprographic policy	Pearson Correlation	1	.765**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
		N	101	101
2	Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.765**	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
		N	101	101

** . The result is significant at P< .05 (2-tailed).

Table 2 displays the Pearson Product Moment Correlation between library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities across South-South Nigeria. The results show an r-value of .765 and a p-value of .000, which is below the 0.05 significance threshold. This demonstrates a very strong correlation between the two variables. Additionally, since the p-value is less than the significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests there is a significant relationship between the library reprographic policy and service delivery in these universities.

Research Question Two:

What is the relationship between the E-Library policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria?

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between the E-Library policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 3: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation on the relationship between the E-Library policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria.

Correlations				
S/N	Items		E-Library policy	Service Delivery
1	E-Library policy	Pearson Correlation	1	.755**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
		N	101	101
2	Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.755**	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
		N	101	101

** . The result is significant at P< .05 (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation between E-Library policy and service delivery in federal universities across South-South Nigeria. The analysis found an r-value of .755 and a p-value of .000, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05. This demonstrates a very strong positive relationship between the E-Library policy and service delivery. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant association between E-Library policy and service delivery in these universities.

Discussion of Findings

The relationship between library reprographic policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria was explored.

Hypothesis 1 demonstrated a significant relationship between reprographic policy and service delivery, indicating that adherence to the policy enhances library services, whereas breaches hinder service delivery. To ensure effective service, libraries should strictly adhere to reprographic policies. This aligns with Clifford and Oghenyerhovwome's (2014) study, which showed that proper implementation of copyright policy by the Nigeria Copyright Commission can reduce copyright law violations. Similarly, consistent enforcement of reprographic policies can resolve management issues and improve library service delivery.

The relationship between e-library policy and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria was investigated.

Hypothesis 2 demonstrated a significant positive correlation between e-library policy and service delivery, highlighting the necessity for individual libraries to develop and effectively implement e-library policies to ensure efficient service delivery. This finding is supported by Okogwu and Ekere (2018), who stressed the importance of collection development policies for electronic resources in improving e-library services. Proper implementation of e-library policies can address issues related to inadequate execution, ultimately enhancing library service delivery.

Conclusion

This study found a strong link between library reprographic policy, e-library policy, and service delivery in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. It concludes that good management of reprographic policy improves library services. Additionally, when professional librarians implement e-library policies, service delivery is further improved.

Based on the findings, the following recommendation is proposed: Library management should strictly comply with copyright laws. Additionally, they should pursue government assistance to hire professional ICT librarians for e-library management.

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